

BIOLOGICAL VALUE OF THE PROTEINS OF BENGAL FISH.

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The biological values of three different varieties of fish, which are commonly consumed, namely, *chingri*, *singhi* (*Saccobranchus fossilis*) and *Air* (*Arius artus*) have been investigated by the growth method. From the results it appears that the biological values of *chingri*, *shinghi* and *air* at 5 and 10% levels are superior to that of casein. Compared among themselves, *air* is superior to both *chingri* and *shinghi* at 5% levels, while at 10% levels they are all approximately equivalent.

As fish constitutes an important article in the daily diet in Bengal, it is desirable to determine the biological value of the proteins of the different varieties of fish, which are commonly consumed. In the present communication investigations of the three varieties, viz., *chingri*, *singhi* (*Saccobranchus fossilis*), and *air* (*Arius arius*) are reported. The biological values of the proteins of these fish were determined by the growth of young rats. When this work was ready for the press, a paper was published by Basu and Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 543), in which figures for the biological value of *shinghi* and *air* proteins were given. Their results are discussed later.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Prior to the biological assay, the fish samples were analysed with reference to their moisture, total nitrogen, ash and fat contents by the methods described by Saha and Guha (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1939, 26, 921).

TABLE I.

Percentage composition of the fish used as sources of protein.

Bengali name.	Zoological name.	Moisture.	Fat.	Total nitrogen.	Protein.	Ash.
Chingri	—	73	1'6	3	18'8	2'1
Singhi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	68	0'6	3'6	22'8	1'7
Air	<i>Arius artus</i>	78'1	1'3	2'5	15'9	1'15

The tests were carried out with young albino rats in separate cages with screened bottoms essentially by the method used by Boas-Fixsen,

TABLE II.
Biological value of proteins of fish and of casein by the growth method.

Materials.	Protein in diet.	No. of rats.	Period of expt.	Increase in weight		Total food intake		Protein intake (mean).	B.V.
				Variation.	Mean.	Variation.	Mean.		
Chingri fish	5 %	4	5 week.	7.22	16	122-174	151.5	8.42	1.90
	10	4	5	22.52	35.25	157-175	169.5	17.45	2.00
	15	4	5	33.48	40.75	164-208	191.5	20.49	1.38
Singhi fish	5	4	5	16.19	17.25	146-187	161.5	8.35	2.09
	10	4	5	38.45	41.25	187-213	203.25	19.91	2.07
	15	4	5	61.72	64.75	190-232	215.0	32.07	2.02
Alr fish	5	3	5	12.15	13.67	126-139	131.0	6.11	2.27
	10	4	5	31.40	37.25	185-212	199.5	19.20	1.94
	15	4	5	44.54	51.5	191-230	216.5	33.01	1.56
Casein	10	4	5	23.34	28.5	169-171	170.0	17.2	1.67
	15	4	5	46.51	48.5	192-194	193.0	27.31	1.66

At 5 % casein level the rats did not show any appreciable growth ; so the results were discarded being of no significant value.

B.V. = gain in weight./protein intake.

Hutchinson and Jackson (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, **28**, 592) and by Basu, Nath and Ghani (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1936, **23**, 811). Each diet consisted of cane sugar (7.5 %), olive oil (12.0 %), cod-liver oil (2.0 %), Steenbock's salt mixture (No. 40) (4.0 %) and calcium carbonate (1.0 %). The fish meal (prepared by mincing, drying at 40° and powdering) was incorporated at such levels in the diets on the basis of their analytical figures (Table I) that they constituted protein levels of 5, 10 and 15 % of the diets. The differences in the fish meal levels were made up by proportionately altering the starch contents of the diets. Four rats were kept on each diet. 0.5 G. of yeast was fed to each rat once a week as a source of vitamin B-complex. It supplied a negligible fraction of the total nitrogen and hence was not taken into account. The actual experimental period for which records were taken began from the 2nd week and lasted for 5 weeks. The biological values were then calculated from the ratio of the total protein intake to the total gain in body weight in five weeks. For comparison, two rats were kept on normal diet consisting of whole wheat and milk, supplemented occasionally by cod-liver oil, and six rats were kept on a synthetic diet containing 5, 10 and 15 % of casein. The data on growth, protein-intake and biological values with different fish meals are summarised in Table II.

DISCUSSION.

The mean biological values of chingri, air, singhi and casein at 5, 10 and 15% protein levels are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III.

Biological values.

Protein.	At 5% level.	At 10% level.	At 15% level.
Air	2.27	1.94	1.56
Singhi	2.09	2.07	2.02
Chingri	1.90	2.00	1.38
Casein	—	1.67	1.66

From the above table, it is clear that the biological values of *chingri*, *singhi* and *air* at 5 and 10% protein levels are superior to that of casein. Compared among themselves, *air* is superior to both *chingri* and *shinghi* at 5% levels, while at 10% levels they are all approximately equivalent. With 5%

casein diet, the rats did not show any appreciable growth. Taking growth as the criterion of biological value of a protein, casein appears, therefore, to be inferior to the proteins of *chingri*, *singhi* and *air* at 5% protein levels.

As the proportion of protein goes up in the diet, however, the biological values approximate to one another. On the whole, all these fish proteins are high-class proteins, *singhi* having the highest biological value at 10 and 15% protein levels. In the paper of Basu and Gupta (*loc. cit.*) concerning the biological values of the proteins of some species of fish, the authors gave the values 1.97 and 1.84 for *air* and *singhi* respectively at 15% protein levels in the diet. In our experiments they are respectively 1.56 and 2.02. The differences may be due to differences in season or source or variety, but all the figures indicate first-class proteins.

With all the sources of protein under investigation, except *chingri*, it is found that the biological value decreases as the concentration of protein in the diet increases. But it is interesting to note that in the case of *chingri*, the biological value at first increases from 1.9 to 2.00 as the percentage of protein in the diet increases from 5 to 10 and then the value decreases from 2.00 to 1.38 as the concentration of protein increases from 10 to 15%. Osborne, Mendel and Ferry (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, 37, 223) record observations showing that the biological value may reach a maximum at a certain protein level and then decline. The *chingri*, however, is not a fish and may conceivably differ in the above respect from the fishes investigated. The subject, however, deserves further study.

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